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STORYTELLING- PILLAR OF METAPHORIC ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of storytelling in metaphoric architecture, exploring how narrative devices and metaphors enhance architectural design, education, and the built environment. Through a review of the literature, case studies, and an examination of student projects, the study explores how storytelling methods like storyboarding and metaphors might be incorporated into architectural creativity and problem-solving. The practical use of metaphoric architecture is demonstrated through case studies of significant structures. According to the research, using metaphoric thinking and narrative in architectural education and practice results in more creative, engaging, and context-sensitive designs, this enhances communication within the profession. This study advances our knowledge of how narrative-driven design methodologies can produce more powerful and evocative architectural solutions.

Keywords: Metaphoric architecture, storytelling, storyboarding, narrative elements, design education, architectural metaphors, creative problem-solving, spatial thinking, built environment, symbolic design, case studies.

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INTRODUCTION

This research paper delves into the importance and influence of storytelling in metaphoric architecture. Storytelling plays a crucial role in metaphoric architecture by providing a framework for interpreting and expressing the implicit forces that shape a place (Matyiku). Metaphors, as fundamental heuristics, aid architects in problem-solving by offering novel perspectives and structuring their approach to design situations. (Casakin, 2019) The use of narrative elements, such as storyboarding, in architectural education enhances students' spatial thinking and expression of ideas through creative representations, fostering a multidisciplinary discourse (Arif Rahman Wahid, 2018).

Additionally, this approach encourages a deeper understanding and communication of architectural ideas, bridging the gap between conceptual thought and practical application. (Sainz, 2014)

It looks at how narrative devices and metaphors can be used to improve design workflows, raise student achievement, and improve the built environment. This study attempts to highlight the difficulties experienced by students and to reveal the differences between metaphor and analogy in architectural design through a comparative examination. In the end, this study aims to demonstrate how narrative in architecture has the power to transform, encouraging creative design approaches and stronger bonds between people and places.

Aim: To determine the role of storytelling in Metaphoric Architecture.

Objectives:

1. Investigate the various aspects of storytelling and its relevance to architectural design.
2. Analyse the principles and methods for incorporating metaphors into architectural design.
3. Investigate the Interplay between Storytelling and Metaphoric Architecture

METHODOLOGY

An introduction and literature review will be presented before the class begins. We will define metaphoric architecture using examples from the visual arts, examine storytelling in architecture through case studies and conversations, and examine their interaction through workshops and analysis. Concepts will be demonstrated through case studies, which will be followed by student design projects. Discussions, comments, an overview of the most important lessons learned, and suggestions for further research will round out the session.

Figure 1: Methodology chart

Key elements of storytelling:

Important components of architectural storytelling include human figures, spatial processes, narrative building, and the spatial storytelling's ability to mediate human knowledge. These components work together to create architectural experiences that are compelling and meaningful. The process of shaping the built environment through language, design elements, and storytelling approaches is known as narrative creation. (Tenna Doktor Olsen Tvedebrink, 2022) Additionally, storytelling can be used to understand people's relationships with their living spaces, impacting their well-being and quality of life. (David Parkinson, 2017). Overall, storytelling plays a crucial role in architectural design by emphasizing human experiences, cultural contexts, and collaborative processes to create meaningful and empathetic spaces.

STORYBOARD STYLE

Figure 2: ‘To Be’ storyboards developed by MSc02 student, Aske Eg

Figure 3: ‘To Be’ storyboards developed by MSc02 student, Aske Eg

Importance of storyboarding presentation:

- i. Storytelling and storyboarding are used to emphasize human well-being in architectural design.
- ii. The approach is inspired by Jørn Utzon, known for blending structural-material expertise with empathy for user experiences.

The storytelling and storyboarding techniques help students integrate knowledge and develop user empathy in architectural design. These methods enable visual communication, idea visualization, and awareness of atmospheres. By creating storyboards of everyday scenarios, students learn to envision and communicate design concepts, blending insights from research with real-life stories. This approach, incorporating elements from filmmaking and cartoons, enhances the ability to convey emotional states and interpret how engineering aspects can support user well-being. It bridges user-oriented, architectural, and engineering principles effectively. (Tenna Doktor Olsen Tvedebrink, 2022).

Figure 4: ‘As Is/ To Be’ storyboards developed by MSc02

Importance of metaphors in architecture:

In architectural design, incorporating metaphors involves using figurative expressions to enhance problem-solving and creativity. Metaphors play a crucial role in how architects conceptualize and address design challenges, particularly during the early stages of the design process. By employing metaphorical expressions, architects can transfer meaning, orient design strategies, and reinforce architectural values.

Metaphors make abstract concepts more tangible, guide formal decisions, and stimulate critical thinking and creativity, especially in design education. For example, metaphorical building forms can address specific design needs, such as preventing sound distortions in performance centers to enhance visitor experiences. Overall, the use of metaphors in architectural design not only aids in solving problems but also enriches the creative process and improves communication within the discipline.

DRED: A program to connect metaphors into architectural design

The program described in the document, (Patricia K. Sheridan, 2022) "Developing Representations of Engineering Design," focuses on using metaphors as a teaching tool to improve students' understanding of engineering design processes. This program employs visual metaphors to help structure and communicate design concepts, enhancing both cognitive and practical aspects of design learning. It critiques traditional design models, offers new metaphorical models, and aims to improve pedagogical approaches by making abstract concepts more tangible and memorable for students. This approach emphasizes the importance of metaphor in shaping understanding and facilitating effective design education. (Patricia K. Sheridan, 2022).

Metaphoric architecture

Metaphoric architecture involves the application of metaphorical thinking in the design process, playing a crucial role in shaping architectural cognition and communication. Architects utilize metaphors to structure their problem-solving approaches, enhance creativity, and convey complex design ideas effectively. This use of metaphor spans from the initial design phase to post-construction assessments, significantly influencing architectural discourse and practice. Architectural metaphors often draw inspiration from various domains, such as the human body, where concepts like "skin" are metaphorically linked to architectural elements beyond mere physical enclosure. This showcases the deep integration of metaphor in architectural concepts and abstractions. By incorporating metaphorical methods in design education, students develop critical thinking skills, make creative decisions, and translate abstract ideas into concrete spatial solutions. This approach ultimately contributes to the evolution of innovative and unique architectural forms. (Caballero, 2014).

Figure 5: Triangle Representation of FDCR

Table 1: Principles of Metaphoric Architecture (metaphoric-architecture)

Key Concept	Description
Symbolism	Buildings serve as symbols that convey deeper meanings beyond their functional use.
Narrative	The design tells a story, guiding the observer through a visual and experiential journey.
Emotional Engagement	The architecture aims to evoke specific emotions and create a memorable experience.
Cultural and Historical References	Designs often incorporate elements that reflect the cultural and historical context of the location.
Abstract Concepts	Metaphors can be drawn from abstract ideas, such as freedom, growth, or harmony, and represented through architectural elements.

Merging storytelling and metaphoric architecture:

Storytelling and metaphoric architecture intertwine to create immersive experiences. Architects use metaphors to communicate complex design concepts, making ideas relatable. They incorporate narrative elements into designs, using spatial sequencing and symbolic forms to evoke emotions. In video games, virtual spaces serve as storytelling tools, blurring real and imagined boundaries. (Caballero, 2014).

Leaders employ metaphors and storytelling to effectively communicate, particularly during crises. By integrating these elements, architects, designers, and leaders can craft experiences that transcend functionality, evoking emotional responses and conveying deeper meanings. This interplay enriches the human experience within the built environment, both physical and virtual.

Example shows architect Zvi hecker explaining how his heinz- Galinski school in Berlin started to take shape and gradually evolved during its construction. (Caballero, 2014)

Figure 6: Sketch and axonometry of Heinz-Galinski school. (Caballero, 2014)

Table 2: evolution of design concept through metaphor (Caballero, 2014)

Aspect	Description
Initial Inspiration	Geometry of a sunflower, focusing on the spirals determining seed growth and the golden progression.
Dynamic and Organic Character	Retained dynamic and organic character of sunflower's seed spirals and sun rays illuminating schoolrooms.
Evolution During Construction	Transformed from "an intricate city" to "a book," showing the evolving nature of the design.
Symbolic Integration	Sunflower's celestial construction symbolizes enlightenment and growth in education.
Architectural Impact	Layout includes streets and courtyards following the paths of orbits and sun rays, integrating natural growth.
Critical Reception	Recognized for using multiple metaphors, highlighting deep metaphorical integration in the design process.

CASE STUDY -1

LOTUS TEMPLE, NEW DELHI

The Lotus Temple in New Delhi, designed by architect Fariborz Sahba and completed in 1986, the lotus flower, a symbol of purity and serenity in many cultures, especially Indian tradition, served as the inspiration for the temple's design. Its nine sides are formed by 27 free-standing marble-clad petals grouped in clusters. With a height of over 40 metres, its central hall has space for up to 2,500 people. The lotus blossom embodies purity and tranquillity, mirroring the Bahá'í Faith's spiritual core of harmony and serenity. The lotus's cultural significance in India strengthens the design's link to its background, while the unfolding petals provide a peaceful area that invites individuals of all religions to meditate. The visitors' contemplative experience is enhanced by the beautiful white marble petals, which evoke calm and cleanliness. The Lotus Temple has received multiple architectural honours and is praised for both its aesthetic appeal and spiritual significance. (metaphoric-architecture).

Figure 7: lotus temple resembling lotus flower

Figure 8: story depicting the process of lotus temple

CASE STUDY- 2

BURJ KHALIFA, DUBAI

The Burj Khalifa in Dubai, designed by architect Adrian Smith of Skidmore, Owings & Merrill and completed in 2010, stands as the tallest building in the world at 828 meters. Inspired by the Hymenocallis flower, a desert plant with long petals extending from a central core, its Y-shaped tripartite floor geometry optimizes residential and hotel space. The Hymenocallis symbolizes growth and elegance, with the tower's verticality representing human aspiration and progress. The upward spiraling design evokes natural growth, symbolizing Dubai's development and prosperity. Reflecting Islamic architecture's emphasis on symmetry and geometric patterns, the design connects the modern skyscraper to the cultural heritage of the Middle East. The building's imposing height and sleek design inspire awe, embodying the ambitious spirit of the city. The Burj Khalifa is a landmark of modern engineering and architectural innovation, symbolizing Dubai's rapid development and aspirations to be a global city. (metaphoric-architecture).

Figure 9: Burj Khalifa resembles hymenocallis flower

CASE STUDY- 3

GHERKIN, LONDON

The Gherkin in London, designed by Norman Foster of Foster and Partners and completed in 2003, stands 180 meters tall with a distinctive curved form and a steel and glass façade. Officially known as 30 St Mary Axe, its design is inspired by the organic shape of a cucumber, allowing for greater aerodynamic performance. Symbolizing sustainability and modernity, the Gherkin reflects the organic forms found in nature. Its unique form creates a dynamic visual experience, symbolizing London's innovative spirit and embracing contemporary architectural trends towards biomimicry. The unconventional design evokes curiosity and admiration, making it an iconic structure in London's skyline. Celebrated for its environmental design, the Gherkin incorporates energy-saving features, making it one of the most sustainable buildings in the city. It has won numerous awards and is a key feature of London's financial district. (metaphoric-architecture).

Figure 10: Gherkin and its biomimicry

CASE STUDY- 4

CASA BATLLO, BARCELONA

Designed by Antoni Gaudí, Casa Batlló is often referred to as the "House of Bones" due to its organic skeletal structure. The building's facade resembles a natural coral formation, with its undulating shape and mosaic tiles. This design metaphorically represents the underwater world, giving the structure a unique, flowing aesthetic. The use of curves and natural forms reflects Gaudí's fascination with nature and his ability to incorporate its elements into functional architecture. This building not only serves as a residence but also as a work of art, showcasing how metaphoric architecture can blend utility with symbolic meaning. (metaphoric-architecture)

Figure 11: resemblance of Casa Balto with natural coral forms

CASE STUDY- 5

National Museum of African American History and Culture, Washington, D.C.

The National Museum of African American History and Culture, designed by David Adjaye, features a distinctive facade inspired by the three-tiered crowns used in Yoruban art from West Africa. This metaphorical design element honors the cultural heritage and history of African Americans. The bronze-coated aluminium panels of the building are adorned with patterns that resemble the ironwork crafted by enslaved African Americans in the southern United States. This museum exemplifies how metaphoric architecture can embody cultural significance and historical context, creating a space that tells a story through its very structure (metaphoric-architecture)

Figure 12: National Museum of African American History and Culture , D.C.

Figure 13: showcasing the cultural identity and history of African American

CASE STUDY- 6

SAGRADA FAMILIA , BARCELONA

The Sagrada Familia in Barcelona, designed by Antoni Gaudí and under construction since 1882, epitomizes metaphoric architecture through its profound use of Christian symbolism and nature-inspired forms. The basilica's design, with 18 spires representing key religious figures and facades narrating Christ's life, guides visitors through a visual and spiritual journey. Gaudí's integration of Catalan modernism and Gothic principles, along with innovative structural techniques like hyperboloids and helicoids, showcases his genius. The Sagrada Familia evokes awe and reverence, creating a transcendent atmosphere through its intricate details and play of light. Gaudí's faith, it attracts millions of visitors. annually and continues to influence architectural innovation while blending historical and modern sustainable practices.

Figure 14: Sagrada Familia

Figure 15: showcase religious figures narrating Christ's life.

Table 3: Comparative case study analysis table

Case Study	Metaphoric Elements	Impact
Lotus Temple, New Delhi	Inspired by the lotus flower, symbolizing purity and tranquillity. Unfolding petals create a serene space for meditation. The design connects with Indian cultural symbolism of beauty, prosperity, and spirituality.	Celebrated for its aesthetic beauty and profound symbolic meaning. Attracts millions of visitors annually and has won numerous architectural awards.
Burj Khalifa, Dubai	Inspired by the Hymenocallis flower, symbolizing growth and elegance. The tower's verticality represents human aspiration and progress. Reflects Islamic architecture's emphasis on symmetry and geometric patterns.	Symbolizes Dubai's rapid development and aspirations to be a global city. Recognized as a landmark of modern engineering and architectural innovation.
The Gherkin, London	Inspired by the organic shape of a cucumber, symbolizing sustainability and modernity. The dynamic visual experience symbolizes London's innovative spirit. Reflects contemporary trends towards bio mimicry in architecture.	Celebrated for its environmental design and sustainability. An iconic structure in London's skyline, it has won numerous awards and is a key feature of the city's financial district.
Sagrada Familia, Barcelona	Rich with Christian symbolism, telling the story of Christ's life through its intricate details. Incorporates organic shapes inspired by nature, reflecting the connection between the divine and natural world.	A symbol of Barcelona and testament to Gaudí's genius. Attracts millions of visitors annually, contributing to the cultural and economic vitality of the city. Influences architectural innovation with its on-going construction.
Casa Batlló, Barcelona	Inspired by the marine world, with undulating forms and colourful mosaics resembling underwater life. The building's facade represents the back of a dragon, tying into local folklore and myth.	A UNESCO World Heritage Site, it is one of Gaudí's masterpieces and a major tourist attraction. Known for its unique, imaginative design and significant cultural impact in Barcelona.

National Museum of African American History and Culture, Washington D.C.	Inspired by the Yoruban crown and the concept of uplifted hands. The corona design symbolizes resilience and upliftment of African American culture. The structure's bronze-colored panels represent African American craftsmanship.	Recognized for its profound cultural and historical significance. A major landmark in Washington D.C., it serves as an important center for education and reflection on African American history and culture.
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SUMMARIZE

The ability of design to reflect cultural and historical settings, elicit strong feelings, and convey deep meanings is best demonstrated by metaphoric architecture. This study illustrates how metaphors enhance architectural innovation and communication using a variety of case studies, including the Lotus Temple, Burj Khalifa, The Gherkin, Sagrada Familia, Casa Batlló, and the National Museum of African American History and Culture. The distinctive metaphorical components and powerful presence of each structure highlight the role that metaphor plays in creating inventive, significant, and emotionally charged built environments. Architects may maintain their ability to build environments that inspire and resonate with a wide range of audiences by incorporating metaphorical thinking into both their practice and teaching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper explores how storytelling through storyboarding and the use of metaphors can drive the creation of innovative architectural designs. By delving into the concept of metaphoric architecture and its significance, the study examines how these approaches enhance project quality and design creativity. It analyses various theories and experiments from different institutions to correlate the intangible elements of storytelling and metaphors with tangible architectural structures. The research encompasses diverse methods and perspectives to demonstrate how ideas, narratives, and abstract thoughts can be effectively translated into concrete architectural forms, ultimately enriching the built environment.

Figure 16: The functional indicators of storytelling

CONCLUSION

This study has highlighted the significant role of storytelling and metaphoric thinking in enhancing architectural design and education. By examining narrative techniques, metaphorical concepts, and their practical applications, we've demonstrated their potential to improve creativity, problem-solving, and communication in architecture. Case studies of iconic structures illustrate how these approaches manifest in practice, creating meaningful and evocative spaces.

Incorporating storytelling and metaphoric thinking in architectural education and practice can lead to more innovative, context-sensitive, and engaging designs. As architecture evolves, these narrative-driven approaches offer exciting possibilities for creating functional, meaningful, and inspiring architectural solutions. This research provides a foundation for further exploration of storytelling's impact on the discipline.

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